

EVALUATION OF MULTILEVEL DELAMINATIONS INDUCED
DURING AIRCRAFT COMPOSITE STRUCTURES ASSEMBLY

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ABSTRACT

With increased usage of advanced composites for primary load carrying aircraft structures, it is becoming even more important for a designer to understand the damage to composite skins and substructure that could develop during assembly. Usually the damage is a composite skin and/or substructure laminate delamination which occurs when unshimmed gaps between skin and substructure are pulled-up during fastener installation.

The results of the study performed at McDonnell Aircraft Company, St. Louis, Missouri for AS4/3501-6 C/E (carbon/epoxy) laminates with induced delaminations are the basis for this paper. The parameters contributing to delamination occurrence, methods for delamination prevention, residual strength of the damaged laminates, and repair methods are discussed.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Delamination; Residual Strength; Failure Mechanism; Testing/Evaluation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are currently used in many primary load carrying military aircraft structures (fuselage, wing, etc.). The usage of composites for the new generation of military aircraft will increase even more. Although there are some tremendous advantages in using composite materials, like high structural efficiency, capability to tailor material to strength and stiffness requirements, high fatigue strength and high compression buckling efficiency, we should be aware of damage that can occur during assembly of composite structures. Usually the damage consists of delaminations in composite skins and substructure.

Two types of delaminations generally occur during C/E laminate manufacturing and assembly: single level and multilevel delaminations. Single level delaminations can be a result of an inclusion between plies, disbonds during tool removal, thermal stresses during the cure cycle for curved laminates, trapped voids, etc. Multilevel delaminations are

usually caused by an interlaminar shear failure during assembly and may be caused by impact or unshimmed gap pull-up during fastener installation.

The multilevel delaminations in AS4/3501-6 unidirectional and woven C/E laminates occurring during composite structures assembly is a primary concern of this paper. Many different tests were performed at McDonnell Aircraft Company to evaluate the factors and parameters involved in creating delaminations, residual strength of delaminated skin and substructure laminates, methods for delamination prevention and repair of delaminations.

2. DELAMINATION OCCURRENCE

A variety of factors can cause delamination during composite parts assembly. Some of the most common causes are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Factors Which Cause Delaminations at Fasteners

By far the most significant factor effecting delamination occurrence is an unshimmed gap between composite skin and spar cap. The delamination can occur in the skin and/or spar cap laminate due to local stresses from composite laminate deflection when fastener is torqued down. This composite material behavior is different from sheet metal assemblies, where sheet metal can be preloaded in this manner without failure. In the case of composites, however, the laminate will sometimes fail in interlaminar shear, creating a multilevel delamination.

To detect delamination in composite laminates sophisticated non-destructive testing techniques are used: ultrasonic through-transmission and pulse echo methods.

A through-transmission C-scan alone is not sufficient for characterizing fastener induced delamination because it does not detect a delamination location through the thickness of the

laminate. A pulse echo A-scan is required for this purpose. An A-scan of the typical fastener induced delamination is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. A-Scan of Typical Fastener Induced Delamination

Typical damage consists of elliptical delamination at several locations through the thickness. The multiple delaminations and extensive matrix cracking are clearly visible in the photomicrograph of typical fastener induced delamination presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Photomicrograph of Typical Fastener Induced Delamination

3. PARAMETERS EFFECTING DELAMINATION OCCURRENCE

The parameters effecting delamination occurrence are: fastener torque, clamp-up force, delaminated laminate stiffness and deflection at failure. To evaluate the above parameters, two different thicknesses of unidirectional C/E skin laminates and various thicknesses of woven C/E spar cap laminates were delaminated simulating assembly environment. The unshimmed gap was varied in length from 76.2 to 152.4 mm (3 to 6 in.) to represent different fastener spacing. Fastener torque versus clamp-up force data are presented in Figure 4. The data show significant difference in fastener torque versus applied load relationship between the short gap span configuration representing 6D fastener spacing and long gap spans representing 8D and 12D fastener spacing. For the short span configuration additional friction is developed between the fastener head bearing surface and the composite laminate countersink surface during fastener torque-up. When the fastener spacing increases, the skin laminate deflection also increases due to the larger bending moment. The larger deflection causes significantly smaller contact area between the fastener head and composite countersink surface, and therefore reduces friction. For the gap spans representing 12D fastener spacing, the coefficient of friction approaches 0.2 (mainly at the fastener threads) and the torque to load relationship becomes a familiar equation:

$$T = 0.2 (D) (P)$$

where: T - Fastener torque (N x m), D - Fastener diameter (m), P - clamp-up force (N)

Figure 4. Fastener Torque vs Bolt Preload Data

Out-of-plane stiffness characteristics data for both undamaged and delaminated laminates were also determined by measuring the slope of a load versus deflection curve for several

specimens. The reduction in stiffness for delaminated skins and spar caps is shown in Figure 5. The thick skin laminates have larger stiffness reduction than thin laminates, while spar caps of different thickness showed the same reduction of about thirty percent. The deflection at failure, where failure was defined as initial delamination occurrence for different skin and spar cap thickness, is presented in Figure 6. In most applications the skin laminate is significantly stiffer than spar cap laminates because of greater thickness, therefore spar cap deflection at failure (Figure 6) is a good indicator for unshimmed gap thicknesses that can cause delaminations. It should be noted that for thick spar caps delaminations could be induced by pulling up unshimmed gaps as small as 0.635 mm (0.025 in.). In cases where the composite skins attach to the metal fittings, the skin laminate deflection at failure will represent critical unshimmed gap.

Figure 5. Stiffness Reduction Factors for Delaminated Laminates

The critical unshimmed gaps should be detected before fastener installation, but if delaminations in the skin are found, the substructure laminates should also be ultrasonically inspected for possible damage.

4. RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF DELAMINATED LAMINATES

The analytical approaches for predicting the behavior of delaminated structures for different failure modes based on local instability, strength considerations, or fracture mechanics predictions are well presented in the literature (References 1 through 4 for example). But most of these methods are for single level delamination where, if the laminate compression load is high enough for the laminate adjacent to the delamination to buckle, the energy released from the buckled plies will propagate the delamination. The

possible modes of failure are a static compression failure of the remaining section or an overall panel buckling failure. The factors affecting single level delamination growth in compression are the through-the-thickness location of the delamination, laminate layup, total laminate thickness and the peel fracture toughness of the material. Although analysis techniques for laminates with multilevel delaminations are still in the development stage, recent tests were conducted at McAir's Structural Testing Facilities to

Figure 6. Deflection at Failure (Delamination Occurrence)

determine behavior of the C/E laminates with induced delaminations up to 76.2 mm (3 in.) in diameter. The residual strength for unidirectional and woven C/E laminates in tension, compression, interlaminar shear and bearing was determined.

The delaminations in test specimens were created by torquing down the fastener over unshimmed gaps between the specimen laminates and simulated substructure. All specimens were ultrasonically inspected to determine size and locations of delaminations through the thickness of the laminate.

The largest strength reduction due to delaminations was the in-plane compression mode of failure. The B-Basis curves for two different thickness laminates at room temperature/dry condition are shown in Figure 7. The data for the specimens with injected delaminations will be discussed in Section 6. For the thick laminate the static compression strength starts to drop at about 45.7 mm (1.8 in.) diameter delaminations, and for the thin laminate at about 6.35 mm (0.25 in.) diameter delamination. Both curves converge when delamination diameter reaches 76.2 mm (3 in.).

The thickness effect on the delaminated laminate ultimate compression strength is shown in Figure 8. All the data presented are for laminates with 50.8 mm (2.0 in.) diameter

delaminations, so the thickness effect could be observed. It is obvious that the delamination effect on thinner laminates is more severe.

The fatigue strength was obtained for a no delamination growth criteria. All specimens were cycled for 24,000 SFH (Spectrum Flight Hours) per typical fighter aircraft fatigue spectrum; and then using the statistical factors from Reference 4, the TLL (Test Limit Load) was increased and specimens cycled for 6,000 SFH until delamination growth

Figure 7. Static Compression Strength for Delaminated Skin Laminates, RT/Dry condition, B - Basis

Figure 8. Compression Strength Reduction vs. Laminate Thickness

occurred. The test spectrum consisted of compression cycles only ($R = -\infty$). The test results are presented in Figure 9. The results show that compression fatigue strength of the delaminated laminates is a high percentage of the ultimate static strength.

The tension tests, as expected, showed no strength reduction for delaminated laminates, because assembly induced delaminations do not cause fibre breakage in the laminate, and the damage is mainly matrix cracks between plies (Figure 3).

Figure 9. Maximum Limit Compression Strain for No Delamination Growth

Although results of the static interlaminar shear tests showed no significant reduction for the delaminated laminates, out-of-plane stiffness was reduced as presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Interlaminar Shear Stiffness Reduction for Delaminated Laminates

For comparison purposes, an out-of-plane stiffness reduction curve was plotted for the case when the delaminated area was assumed to have no stiffness. Despite a large data scatter, it was observed that while delaminated specimens maintained most of the undamaged static interlaminar shear strength, the out-of-plane stiffness for test panels was reduced.

A series of tests were also performed to develop bearing strength reduction for the skin and spar laminates with delaminations at loaded holes. The failure criteria for the bearing stress allowable in delaminated laminates were hole elongation (maximum elongation - 4% of the hole diameter) or laminate failure. The B-Basis values for the undamaged and delaminated C/E laminates at 93° C (200° F)/1% moisture conditions are shown in Figure 11. For the D/t ratios below 1.1 the delamination around the loaded hole does not effect the laminate bearing strength.

Figure 11. Bearing Strength Reduction for Delaminated Laminates; (93° C (200° F)/Wet), B-Basis

5. DELAMINATED LAMINATE REPAIRS

The repair methods for delaminated laminates depend on the type of loading and expected failure mode. For delaminated laminates loaded in compression two types of structural repairs were verified: bonded titanium patch and adhesive injection. The static tests demonstrated that the bonded titanium patch repair restored the delaminated laminate strength to its undamaged capability. The fatigue tests for bonded titanium patch repairs showed no delamination growth or failure when cycling per typical fighter aircraft fatigue spectrum.

The injection of a low viscosity adhesive into delaminated laminate showed significant compression static and fatigue strength improvement (Figures 7 through 9). The adhesive

was injected under pressure into pre-drilled holes in the delaminated area using the injection device shown in Figure 12. The recommended minimum successful injection is about 80 percent of the delaminated area; however, test results confirmed that it does not take a lot of support to prevent the delaminated area from buckling.

The tests showed no significant laminate interlaminar shear or bearing strength improvement with injection repairs. Some feasible repairs to improve out-of-plane stiffness are bonded or bolted patches. Standard bearing repairs such as oversized holes, bushings and structural shims should be used for the laminates with delamination around the holes.

Figure 12. Delamination Injection Set-Up.

6. METHODS FOR DELAMINATION PREVENTION

Since the delaminations are induced by torquing down fasteners where unshimmed gaps exist between the wing skin and the substructure, the way to prevent delaminations from occurrence is to eliminate unshimmed gaps. Most of the delaminations occur at spar and rib intersections, or where a composite spar attaches to the metal fitting. It is very difficult to maintain the tolerances required to eliminate gaps or use solid metal or composite shims throughout the entire assembly. In many cases moldable plastic shimming is used for large composite assemblies.

Plastic shim is a two-component epoxy which is formed to shape by applying a required amount between skin and substructure. Temporary fasteners are installed until the shim solidifies. The shim fills in low spots and squeezes out at high spots and therefore eliminates gaps. It cures (hardens) at room temperature and becomes an integral part of the structure.

The tests were performed to determine how plastic shim thickness affects laminate bearing strength. The results of the tests are presented in Figure 13. Bearing strength based on a

four percent hole elongation criteria is reduced as the liquid shim thickness increases. The fatigue tests proved the durability of the plastic shim over the life of the aircraft. A decreased fastener fatigue life can also occur; and should be accounted for.

Figure 13. Static Bearing Strength Reduction for Joints With Shims and Gaps

7. CONCLUSIONS

During composite structure assembly multilevel delaminations in the C/E skin and/or C/E substructure could be created by pulling out unshimmed gaps as small as 0.635 mm (0.025 in.) when fasteners are installed. One method to minimize the effect of gaps is the selective use of metal or plastic moldable shims.

The largest strength reduction for C/E laminates with multilevel delaminations is for static compression loads; however, C/E laminates are fairly strong with significantly large delaminations. Thin laminate compression strength is affected more by multilevel delamination than thick laminate compression strength. Delaminated static strength scatter for compression is low, and more strength scatter exists in small delaminations than in large delaminations. The compression fatigue strength of C/E laminates with delaminations up to 76.2 mm (3.0 in.) in diameter is a high percentage of static ultimate strength.

The tests confirmed that laminate RT/Dry and Cold/Dry tension strength was not affected by multilevel delaminations.

The induced multilevel delamination in C/E laminates significantly reduces out-of-plane stiffness of the laminates. This is probably not a strength problem since delaminations incurred during assembly occur at rib/spar intersections, i.e. the corners of skin panels where the transverse shears are small. Finite element modeling supports this supposition. Interlaminar shear strength is not substantially reduced by moderate-sized multilevel delaminations.

The maximum static bearing strength reduction for C/E laminates with delaminations at the loaded holes is only 15 percent. For bolt diameter to laminate thickness ratios below 1.10

there is no bearing strength reduction due to delaminations local to the fastener hole. Four percent bolt hole elongation was used as failure criteria.

Injection of the delamination with low viscosity adhesive significantly improves both static and fatigue compression strength of delaminated laminates, but the following observations should be noted:

- Although it does not take a lot of support to prevent a delaminated area from buckling under compression loads, the injection adhesive should fill at least 80 percent of the delaminated area for adequate fatigue strength.
- Static and fatigue compression tests at hot/wet conditions should be performed for the specimens with an injected delamination to verify the injected adhesive strength at elevated temperature and moisture.
- Another concern for injected delaminations is out-of-plane loads (pressure, kick loads, etc.) that could result in an interlaminar shear failure of the injected adhesive bond, and possible subsequent compression failure of the laminate. Static and fatigue hot/wet interlaminar shear tests should be performed.

Injection of adhesive around fastener holes to improve bearing strength was not productive. A bonded titanium patch repair for a laminate with a multilevel delamination restores static and fatigue compression strength to undamaged laminate level.

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